

DETERMINING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE FACULTY JOB PERFORMANCE AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Academic Institutions play a significant role in the holistic development of every student. It provides an avenue to students to have the opportunity to harness their knowledge, skills, characters, values, and abilities. One common indicator of academic achievement is the over-all grade received by the students in a course as a reflection of their overall performance over a specific period of time. On one hand, in a given specific period of time, faculty members are also evaluated based from their job performance. This study sought to describe the relationship between the students' academic achievement and the job performance of the faculty members in the College of Information and Communication Technology at the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology during the second semester of Academic Year 2019-2020. Results revealed that the majority of the students in their major courses got a satisfactory to outstanding performances. On the other hand, the job performance of the faculty members ranges from very satisfactory to outstanding. Results show that there is a positive relationship between the academic achievement of the students and the job performance of the faculty members in the college ($p=0.035$, $r=.423$). The researchers suggest that the faculty members continuously improve their craft and hone their expertise by attending trainings and other relevant capacity-building activities in order to incessantly contribute to the holistic development of the students. Future studies may be also done to look at the factors on how to

further strengthen and improve the academic achievement of the students and the performance of the faculty members.

Keywords— Academic Achievement, Descriptive-Correlational Research, Job Performance

INTRODUCTION

Schools have two main actors in the teaching and learning process known as the teacher and the student. No process of lesson delivery and learning will be realized without them. As actors of the process, they have both the responsibility to be acted upon. Teachers, as one of the actors in the delivery of education, have the most crucial role, which is to facilitate learning through mentoring and nurturing. They are tasked to share knowledge with the students. (education.gov.gy, 2020). To do so, each teacher should undergo mandatory schooling, training, and regulatory examinations to be entitled as one. This ensures that individuals who desire to teach can perform their job effectively since it is a sensitive duty to fulfill. (learnhowtobecome.org, 2020).

Betterteam.com (2020) enumerated the job responsibilities of a teacher. Responsibilities include developing and issuing educational content including notes, tests, and assignments, and supervise classes to ensure all students are learning in a safe and productive environment. Teachers also need to organize supplies and resources for lectures and presentations and deliver personalized instruction to each student by encouraging interactive learning. Planning and implementing educational activities and events and ensuring that the classroom is clean and orderly are essential teachers' responsibilities. In schools, teachers also prepare and distribute periodic progress reports and semester report cards, attend parent-teacher meetings, evaluate and document students' progress, and allocate and grade homework, assignments, and tests.

As part of teachers' responsibilities in the teaching and learning process, they formulate assessments and evaluations. Assessment for Learning (AFL) is a teaching and learning method that provides feedback to enhance students' success. (Cambridge Assessment International Education, 2020). The purpose of AFL is to retrieve the level of understanding of the students to the specific learning objective delivered through the lessons. It can be in the form of tests, quizzes, performance tasks, or presentations. Initially, these activities are the necessary measurement of teaching and learning progress.

On the other hand, students are present to the schools because they are the ones who need to receive learnings. Every child needs to be at school to acquire knowledge, and it happens over a series of processes and promotions. They start to be in a pre-school up to earning a degree in college or more. School provides an environment to learn the primary up to professional skills, gain knowledge, develop talents, learn from experts, and meet friends. (teaching-jobs.org, 2019).

As students, their primary responsibility is to perform the activities prepared by teachers in the learning process. Allen (2005) stated that grades are valid measures of academic achievement of classroom learning. These are reflections of a series of assessments to determine the level of learning and understanding of the students. Grades can be quantified using scales or transmutations.

Teaching and learning are the combined processes where an educator assesses learning needs, establishes specific learning objectives, develops teaching and learning strategies, implements a plan of work, and evaluates the instructional outcomes (Clause, 2015). In the concept of formal education, teachers are transferring knowledge to their students. It can be done in different modes depending on whichever applies to the students. To put it simply, lessons are the teacher's input within the delivery of the lesson during the class and the way students take it from the teacher is the process. Finally, the achievements of

the students upon learning can be referred to as the output. Both the teachers and the students have their tasks done and evaluated. Teachers are being observed and assessed by their superiors such as the Dean or the Principal using criterion-based assessment instruments while students are also evaluated using their outputs and performance during activities.

This study aims to determine if there is a relationship between students' academic achievement and the teacher's job performance. Using the result of the immediate supervisor's class observation, teachers' performance can be quantified against the grade scale of the students they handled as determinants of academic achievement.

Statement of the Problem

In general, this study sought to determine the relationship between the faculty job performance and students' academic achievement in the College of Information and Communications Technology. Specifically, it described the following:

1. How may the teacher's job performance be described in terms of;
 - 1.1. Teaching Strategy (Teacher);
 - 1.2. Students; and
 - 1.3. Learning Environment
2. How may the students' academic achievement in the major courses during the second semester of academic year 2019-2020 be described?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the faculty job performance and the students' academic achievement?

Conceptual Framework

Evaluating the students' grades and the result of the faculty member's performance are ways to determine the relationship between them. However, many variables can also be considered to determine achievements and performance.

Walberg's academic achievement theory from Reynolds & Walberg (1992) posits that individual students' psychological characteristics and their immediate psychological environments influence educational outcomes (cognitive, behavioral, and attitudinal). It is also lifted from Campbell (2015) that Individual work role performance drives the entire economy. Thus, this study checked if these theories are related to each other. Thus, it is empirical to know the existing relationship between student achievement in academics and the Faculty members' performance in doing their job.

In this context, the administration can devise programs to motivate the faculty more to produce additional numbers of student achievers.

Figure 1: Research Paradigm

METHODOLOGY

The researchers used the descriptive-correlational research method. Descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon. (McCombes, 2020) It aims to describe the level of student achievements and the job performance of the faculty members.

In this study, the researchers used total enumeration sampling to satisfy the researchers' standard identifiers. In this study, the samples were comprised of the enrolled students of the Bachelor of Science in Information Technology in the second semester of academic year, 2019-2020, and the faculty members of the College of Information and Communications Technology. The researchers used the population mentioned above so that the accurate correlation can be lifted from them. The researchers were able to retrieve 100% responses from the available data.

The instrument used to measure the faculty members' job performance is based on the AACUP Form 3c or the Observation Form- Instruction. This instrument is used by the Area Chairman to evaluate the faculty's performance in their duty as facilitators of learning every month. This instrument consists of three areas, namely; Teacher, Student, and Learning Environment. On the other hand, the academic achievement of the students were based from their course grade.

The researchers used weighted mean to describe the job performance of the faculty members in terms of teacher, students, and learning environment. Frequency distribution was used to describe the academic achievement of the student. Finally, the test of relationship was used to answer research problem number 3 to find out if there is a significant relationship between the Students' Academic Achievement and Job Performance of Faculty Members.

Table 1:
Scoring Guide Rubric

Range	Verbal Description
4.21- 5.00	Outstanding
3.41- 4.20	Very Good
2.61- 3.40	Good
1.81- 2.60	Fair
1.00-1.80	Poor

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Faculty Job Performance

Figure 2: Teacher Factor

Figure 2 describes that the faculty members are outstanding at mastering the subject matter, organizing the lesson, managing the classes, methods, and techniques, personality and grooming, promotion of desirable values and habits, communication skills, and the use of instructional materials.

In summary, faculty members got the highest mean of 4.56 on the mastery of subject matter. This reflects that the faculty members under the College of Information and Communications Technology performed well in their lessons with proficiency. According to Liakopoulou (2011), this skill, which belongs to the pedagogical content knowledge, contributes to teachers' effectiveness. On the other hand, the awareness of the current issue was scored with a mean of 4.07.

Cezer et al. (2015) stated that teachers should be aware of the different issues inside his/her classroom in order for a teacher to provide support. The data above show that the faculty members have an excellent performance in this.

It can be reflected that faculty members in the College of Information and Communications Technology are capable of doing their jobs from planning up to delivering instruction. Keeping from the same level of performance in the next academic years may improve the quality of teaching in the BSIT program. It may also be considered that faculty can be sent to training and workshops to share more ideas with them. It is also fundamental for teachers to review and relearn classroom management basics, such as teaching, developing instructional materials, and effective methods and techniques.

Figure 3: Student Factor

Figure 3 shows the weighted mean from the data gathered, including the evaluation involving the students' state. Student-Teacher Interaction was scored 4.00; this comprises of the involvement of the student in the teaching process. Preparedness refers to the readiness of both the student and the teacher in

delivering and accepting the lesson. It was scored with a weighted mean of 3.99. Communication Skills with a mean score of 3.94 includes the language used to explain the subject matter being discussed. It also refers to the concept that the students understand the teacher. Finally, the awareness of the current issues in the classroom atmosphere and the students was scored with a mean of 3.83.

Though the data shown above were interpreted as Very Good, the Student-Teacher Interaction was scored highest. Students' and teachers' interaction plays a vital role in the student's engagement in the learning process. According to Pascarella & Terenzini (1991, 2005), as cited by Hu (2015), "The inherent ideas within student engagement are the purposeful activities that are geared towards a wide range of student outcomes, such as persistence, satisfaction, achievement, and academic success". On the other hand, it can also be seen that Students' Awareness of Current Issues was scored lowest. A study by Alsubaie (2015) stresses that awareness in the environment is essential because it introduces new thoughts and ideas to students. Thus, it is natural to stay sensitive about the issues that are present inside the classroom itself.

The data presented above shows that the faculty members, aside from their primary task to deliver lessons, are also very good at engaging their students to learn from the discussion through interactions, being prepared, being understood, and tactfully attending to some student issues. Teachers can also formulate more activities that involve all their students in the learning process like collaboration, presentation, or interactive discussions. They must also find enough time to read their materials to deliver the lesson well. Avoiding jargon or translating their discussion into shallow language can also help the students understand the lesson well. Finally, being sympathetic to the students is also necessary.

Figure 4: Learning Environment Factor

Figure 4 presents the scores from the Learning Environment Factor of Faculty Observation. The learning environment may relate to an orientation to education, a cultural context, or a physical environment in which teaching and learning occur.

It can be seen that Freedom from Distraction scored 3.71, which means that during the classes conducted by the teacher, they make sure that their area is free from noises and other disturbance. Teachers also made sure that the classroom is well ventilated with a score of 3.58. Learning can also be useful with adequate facilities; this factor was scored with 3.86. Orderliness and Cleanliness as part of the environment housekeeping were also scored 3.73.

The factors in the learning environment were interpreted as very good. All the factors mentioned above in the learning setting is evident that the study conducted by Schneider and Mark (2002) is valid as they stressed out, "school facilities affect learning. Spatial configurations, noise, heat, cold, light, and air

quality bear on students' and teachers' ability to perform. Needed are clean air, good light, and a quiet, comfortable, and safe learning environment. The review asserts that this can be and generally has been achieved within the limits of existing knowledge, technology, and materials; it simply requires adequate funding and competent design, construction, and maintenance".

To facilitate better performance of the teacher and the student outcomes, it may be considered that the administration may conduct a physical survey to find out what needs to be added, repaired, or reconstructed concerning the safe and healthy teaching and learning environment. They may also include the number of usable facilities against the number of students so that learners may have experiential learning, which will help them apply the lessons they merely watch and hear.

Students' Academic Achievement

Figure 5: Frequency Distribution of Students' Academic Achievement

Figure 5 represents the count and percentage of the grades achieved by the students in their major subjects. The students' final grade is translated into the Grade Equivalent from 1.00(highest)- 5.00(lowest). Among the 4020 grades that has been retrieved, 0.20% got failed remarks or 5.00, 6.09% got 3.00, 5.42% got 2.75, 8.81% got 2.50, 14.80% got 2.25, 19.43% got 2.00, 21.14% got 1.75, 14.85% got 1.50, 7.61% got 1.25 and 1.64% got the highest score of 1.00.

The presented data concludes that only 8 out of 4020 grades are failed while the rest, with the count of 4012, is passed. This implies a positive student achievement in their major subjects during the 2nd Semester of Academic Year 2019-2020.

According to a study conducted by Johnson (2014), it states that the high passing rate of students contributes to the school's performance as a whole. It can be reflected that the academic council may arrange motivations for teachers to arrange activities that may maximize the skills of the students to produce excellent outcomes that will be reflected in the grades. To this extent, the students will have better achievement. It is a win-win solution that will help the student and the institution as well.

The Relationship between Faculty Job Performance and Students' Academic Achievement

Table 2:

The Relationship between Faculty Job Performance and Students' Academic Achievement

Variables		Students' Academic Achievement	Decision
Faculty Job Performance	Correlation Coefficient	0.423*	Significant Relationship
	p-value	0.035	

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

Understanding the relationship between the faculty job performance and the students' academic achievement provides an opportunity to assess whether the knowledge, capabilities, values, skills, and characteristics of the faculty members can contribute to the holistic development of the students. Results revealed a positive relationship between variables ($p\text{-value}=0.035$). This indicates that the better the job performance of the faculty members, the better the academic achievement of the students. Job performance may be attributed to the job satisfaction of the faculty members. According to Stoll-Lollis (2015), the job satisfaction of the teachers has a direct impact on their instructional performance. Aside from that, teacher retention in the academic institution, positive school climate, and increased student achievement can be attributed to the job satisfaction of the teachers. Results of this study indicates that the faculty members of the college are also satisfied with their job, resulting to a better job performance which positively affects student achievement.

CONCLUSION

Academic Institutions play a significant role in the holistic development of every student. It provides an avenue to students to have the opportunity to harness their knowledge, skills, characters, values, and abilities. This study determined the relationship between the job performance of the faculty members in the College of Information and Communications Technology and the students' academic achievement. Results revealed that the majority of the students in their major courses got a satisfactory to outstanding performances. On the other hand, the job performance of the faculty members ranges from very satisfactory to outstanding. Results show that there is a positive relationship between the academic achievement of the students and the job performance of the faculty members in the college ($p=0.035$, $r=.423$). The researchers suggest that the faculty members continuously improve their craft and hone their expertise by attending trainings and other relevant capacity-building activities in order to incessantly contribute to the holistic development of the students.

RECOMMENDATION

Based from the results of this study, the following are the recommendations drawn by the researchers:

1. The faculty members must continuously improve their craft and expertise in the field of IT by joining different local, national, and international workshop to contribute to the holistic development of the students;
2. The college may devise faculty-training program aligned to the specializations of every faculty member to cultivate their talents and capabilities;
3. Students may also be exposed to other learning experiences in order to further develop their skills.

4. Future study may be conducted considering other relevant factors that affects job performance and students' academic achievement.

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